

Contributory Effect of Value Added Tax to Tax Revenue in Nigeria

**Olakunbi Taiwo-Taiwo (PhD), Omolara Campbell (PhD), and
Oluwatosin Adesina (PhD)**

*Department of Economics & Development Studies,
Lead City University, Ibadan.*

Abstract

This study examines the contributory effect of value-added tax on the level of tax revenue in Nigeria using time series data spanning from 2010 Q1 to 2021 Q4. The data used in this study were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin. The technique used for estimation in this study was the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, which was employed to examine the short-run and long-run impact of value-added tax on tax revenue. The result shows that value-added tax has a negative and insignificant contributory impact on tax revenue in the long and short run. The study recommends that government should work at increasing the level of VAT in the country until it contributes positively to the overall tax revenue and the economy.

Keywords: Value-added tax, tax revenue, ARDL

Introduction

Every government is saddled with the responsibility of looking after the welfare of its people and also providing for their needs in one way or the other. In other words, for this to be possible, the government will be in need of funds to fulfil this responsibility. Funds can be generated using taxes. Taxation is the compulsory levy imposed by the government on economic agents such as firms and households (Goode, 1984). Every tax must be based on a valid statute. If there is no valid statute, no legitimate tax can be imposed (Okafor, 2012). It is a financial charge or other levy imposed upon a taxpayer (an individual or legal entity) by a state or the functional equivalent of a state, usually

considered a major source of government revenue for the funding of various public expenditures (Edame and Okoi, 2014). Tax is a major source of revenue for the government. The flows from this revenue are used to provide public goods, maintain law and order, defend against external aggression, and regulate trade and business in order to ensure social and economic processes (Edame, 2008). Tax revenue has accounted for a small proportion of total government revenue over the years because the bulk of the nation's revenue needed for development purposes is derived from oil. Among the various types of taxes (i.e. companies income tax, petroleum profit tax, personal income tax, withholding tax, education tax,

stamp duties, information and technology tax, capital gain tax etc.) collected by the government, value-added tax (VAT) is a consumption tax that is relatively easy to administer and difficult to evade, and it has been embraced by many countries world-wide which is because VAT provides an avenue for citizens to contribute funds through a compulsory levy to help the government in achieving their objectives (FIRS, 1993). VAT increases government revenues without charging affluent taxpayers more, unlike income taxes which charge them more. Also, it is easy and more uniform than the traditional sales tax, with a smaller amount of compliance issues. Ultimately, VAT basically pays off for the communal service and infrastructure provided in an economy by the government and financed by its taxpayers that were used in providing the products or services. In many developing countries, VAT has become a major source of revenue to Sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries such as Benin, Côte d'Ivoire, Guinea, Kenya, Madagascar, Mauritius, Niger, Senegal, Togo and Nigeria as this was adopted in the 1980/90s (Kaisa, Mika and Jukka, 2019).

Furthermore, VAT was introduced into Nigeria's tax system as a means of increasing government revenue, given the steadily rising costs of governance on one hand and the dwindling and erratic returns from petroleum, Nigeria's principal source of revenue. VAT in Nigeria today replaced the existing sales tax, which had been in operation under the Federal Government Legislated Decree No. 7 of 1986 (Okoli and Afolabi, 2015). The interesting aspect of Nigeria's Value Added Tax is that it is very low, which has stood at a single rate of 5% in 1996, not

until the recent increase to 7.5% in 2020. The country has one of the lowest VAT rates in the world and in Africa. To mention but a few, Ghana has a rate of 12.5%, Angola, Botswana, and Egypt have a rate of 14%, while South Africa, Eswatini, Ethiopia, Sierra Leone, Equatorial Guinea, Seychelles, Mauritius, and Namibia have their rate at 15% (Statista, 2021). Due to problems like poor accountability, corruption of tax officials, tax avoidance and evasion and so on, which are faced by the tax administration in Nigeria, the administration has suffered several limitations in the discharge of their responsibility. Several studies have been carried out on this study by different researchers' on VAT and tax revenue (Karumba, 2016; Keen 2010; Saeed, Ahmad and Zaman, 2012), but little attention has been given to the issue of VAT and how they significantly influence economic growth. Economic growth comes into the picture when revenue is generated, and the government is able to fulfil its role in the economy. Therefore, this study seeks to underscore the contributory effect of VAT on Tax revenue in Nigeria. The time scope that will be used in this study will cover from 2010 to 2021 quarterly data from one to four. The rest of the paper is structured as follows: section two for literature review, section three is for theoretical framework and methodology, section four is for data analysis and interpretation, and section five concludes the paper.

Literature review

The relevant studies reviewed for this study are presented in this section. Ofishe (2015) investigated the impact of value-added tax on economic growth in Nigeria so as to find out if

revenue from VAT has any significant impact on economic growth. The study carried out its investigation from 1994 to 2012. The technique used was OLS. After having analyzed the objectives using the technique chosen, the result showed that there is a positive and significant impact that VAT has on total revenue in Nigeria. Total revenue growth also had a substantial effect on economic growth. It is concluded that Value Added Tax has a significant impact on the economic growth of Nigeria. Government should put in place measures that will ensure that revenue obtained from VAT is effectively and efficiently utilized to grow the economy and enhance infrastructural development. Efuntade (2020) examined value-added tax and its effect on revenue generation in Nigeria from 1999 to 2019. The technique used in the study is the VECM method of analysis. The findings show that value-added tax has a significant positive relationship with revenue generation. PIT has a positive and significant impact on oil revenue. CIT also has a positive and significant relationship with total public borrowing. Government should ensure strategies that will help maintain adequate accounting procedures in the tax system to enhance the efficiency of VAT.

Ubesie, Igweonyia and Ubaka (2019) analysed a causal and long-run nexus between value-added tax and the economic growth of Nigeria from 1994 to 2017 to examine the implication of VAT on revenue generation in Nigeria and also to know how VAT affects the economic growth. Data was sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). The technique used in this study is Vector Error

Correction Mechanism (VECM), Granger Causality Model, and Vector Auto regressive (VAR). Findings using this technique showed that Value Added Tax and Tax revenue both have short and long run significant influences on the growth of the Nigerian economy. It is recommended that the economy restructure for taxation to serve as a major source of non-oil revenue for the Nigerian economy. There are many other recommendations in the study. Odunsi (2022) examined the effect of VAT on Nigeria's revenue generation and economic growth. The data was gathered from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin, Federal Inland Revenue Service reports, the Federal Office of Statistics, and the Federal Ministry of Finance for a period of twenty-five (25) years (1994-2018). The data was evaluated using the regression (OLS approach), and the result indicated that the impact of VAT on economic growth and tax revenue generation in Nigeria was positive and significant. The study suggests that the government should establish appropriate tax management to increase revenue and implement better economic policies and macroeconomic changes.

Onuora, Okegbe and Ezejiolor (2017) found out that: Value Added Tax (VAT) contributes to the total tax revenue of the nation, the Gross Domestic Product of the nation and also its revenue has impact on the actual VAT with data gathered from CBN statistical bulletin, Federal Inland Revenue Services federal ministry of finance, and journals. The data obtained were analyzed using simple regression analysis over a period of thirteen years (2003 to 2015). The

recommendation of this study, among others, is that governments' agencies are advised to be loyal and disciplined when utilizing public funds obtained from VAT. Ugwu, Peter and Udolu (2019) investigated the effect of VAT on total government revenue in Nigeria from 1994 to 2017 using Ordinary Least Square (OLS). This study generated data from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and the Federal Inland Revenue Service. The result of the study revealed that value-added tax benefits the Nigerian economy; this implies that value-added tax is statistically significant to government revenue in Nigeria. The recommendation is that value-added tax administration should be sustained while all known administrative ambiguity should be covered for VAT revenue to keep contributing more significantly to the government's total revenue. Keen and Lockwood (2007) conducted a panel study of 143 countries, exploring the causes and consequences of the spread of value-added tax. The findings revealed that adopting VAT by some countries leads to an increase in revenue generated while others do not, thus indicating mixed results. Saeed, Ahmad and Zaman (2012) analyzed the revenue effect of the value-added tax on revenue in the SAARC region from 1995 to 2010. The authors said the adoption of VAT in some parts of the region has proved to be a viable instrument for collecting tax revenue. The study indicates that VAT has been an effective tax instrument for most of the SAAR countries that adopted this tax form, as it has increased their GDP-to-revenue ratio. Olatunji (2009) used simple percentages and chi-square to analyze the effectiveness of the administration of value-

added tax on government revenue, consumption patterns of consumers and output growth in Nigeria. The result was subjected to 433 returned questionnaires out of 550 administered. The result shows that value-added tax has been effectively administered and increased government revenue and economic growth. The author noted that the administration of tax would have an economic implication on the consumption patterns of Nigerians.

Onaolapo, Aworemi and Ajala (2013), in their study, investigated the impact of VAT, petroleum profit tax, company income tax and education tax on the total revenue generated within the periods of 2001-2010. It indicates that VAT has positive and significant impact on revenue generation when regressed alone and also with petroleum tax but negatively adding company income tax and education tax as regressors. The study concludes that value-added tax is advantageous to Nigeria. They argued that for the economy to attain growth and development, adequate revenue must be generated to sufficiently provide social amenities and infrastructure.

The results obtained in the literature, shows that there exists a gap in knowledge as there is little empirical studies on the contributory effect of VAT on tax revenue in Nigeria. Hence, this study will fill the gap in knowledge.

Methodology

The study employs the Laffer Curve Theory, which is found relevant towards illustrating the relationship between VAT and tax revenue. It was believed that an increase in tax rates would increase tax revenue, but this was countered by

Laffer who stated that the more money one takes from a business in the form of taxes, the less money it will be willing to invest, and a business will find ways to protect its capital from taxation or to relocate all or a part of its operations overseas. He argued that this means less total revenue as tax rates rise and that the economic effects of reducing incentives to work and invest by raising tax rates would adversely affect the economy. Following the theoretical framework, this study specifies the empirical model of the contributory effect of value-added tax on tax revenue in Nigeria in equation (1):

$$LTAXR_t = \pi_0 + \pi_1 CCIED_t + \pi_2 CCIEDSQ_t + \pi_3 CFTAX_t + \pi_4 CFTAXSQ_t + \pi_5 CVAT_t + \pi_6 CVATSQ_t + \varepsilon_t$$

The tax revenue (LTAXR) in this study is the total amount of tax collected in a year. CCIED and CCIEDSQ represent the contribution of Custom, Imports and Excise Duties and its square, CFTAX and CFTAX are the contribution of Federal Inland Revenue Service Tax and its square, while CVAT and CVATSQ represent the Value Added Tax and its square. π_0, π_1 to π_6 are the model's constant value and coefficients of the variables, respectively, while ε is the error term and t is time.

The data used in this study were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, 2020. The data that will be used for this study are basically time series data covering 2010:Q1 to 2021:Q4, a period of twenty-five years with 100 observations based on the availability of data for some of the variables.

The dependent variable is measured by tax revenue (TAXR), while the independent variables are Custom, Import and Excise Duties (CCIED), Firs tax (FTAX), and Value Added Tax (VAT).

This study utilized the Auto regressive distributed Lag (ARDL) to estimate the parameters. The pre estimation test that was carried out were unit root test and bound test while for the post estimation test; normality, serial correlation, heteroskedasticity, CUSUM and CUSUMSQ were also carried out.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The study presents the description of the data series by evaluating the different statistical measures like mean, median, standard deviation, maximum and minimum values, skewness, kurtosis and Jarque-Bera values. The summary of statistics for customs, import and excise duties (CCIED), Firs Tax (FTAX), and Value Added Tax (VAT) are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summarised Statistics

	CCIED	CFTAX	CVAT	LTAXR
Mean	22.96	41.62	37.1	26.02
Median	23.45	37.39	38.75	25.93
Maximum	29.77	73.82	51.03	26.83
Minimum	12.36	28.15	25.45	25.28
Std. Dev.	3.34	11.22	5.95	0.37
Skewness	-0.77	1.26	-0.21	0.27
Kurtosis	3.8	3.94	2.65	2.3
Jarque-Bera	6.01	14.51	0.6	1.55
Probability	0.05	0	0.74	0.46
Sum	1102.05	1997.58	1780.62	1249.12
Sum Sq. Dev.	523.66	5919.38	1661.23	6.42
Observations	48	48	48	48

Source: Authors' computation (2022)

The summarised statistics show that the average values of the Contribution of Custom, Import and Excise Duties (CCIED), the contribution of Firs Tax (FTAX) and the contribution of Value Added Tax (VAT) and tax revenue (LTAXR) were 22.96, 41.62, 37.1 and 26.02 respectively. The table also shows CVAT and CCIED are negatively skewed while CFTAX

and LTAXR are positively skewed. It also shows that CCIED and CFTAX are leptokurtic while CVAT and LTAXR are platykurtic. The Jarque-Bera values indicate that the data series is not normally distributed at 5% level of significance.

The study used Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test which is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test

Variables	Levels		First Difference		Conclusion
	ADF Test	Test Critical	ADF Test	Test Critical	
LTAXR	0.58	-2.603	-15.743	-3.589***	I(1)
CCIED	-4.349	-3.592***	-	-	I(0)
CFTAX	-1.638	-2.603	-11.924	-3.589***	I(1)
CVAT	-2.377	-2.603	-14.077	-3.589***	I(1)

*, **, *** represent 10%, 5% and 1%, respectively

Source: Author's compilation from Eviews

The ADF unit root test results shown in Table 2 indicate three variables are integrated at the first difference I (1) while only CCIED is integrated at the level I (0) in the study.

Table 3: Bounds Tests

F-Statistics	Value	I (0)	I (1)	Decision
4.957	1%	3.27	4.39	Co integration exists

Source: Author’s compilation from Eviews

The result in Table 3 shows that the F statistics 4.957 is seen to be higher than the upper bound of the critical value of 4.39 at a 1% significance level. This implies that there is cointegration among the variables. The study, therefore, proceeds to use ARDL model, which is shown in Table 4.

In Table 4, it shows both the long-run and short-run results. In the table, the result of the adjusted R-squared indicates that only a 96.56%

variation in tax revenue is explained. The Durbin-Watson statistics of 2.04 indicates that there is no serial correlation in the model and also, the overall test using the F-statistics (89.296) is statistically significant at 1% level of significance, showing that the model is well specified and statistically significant. In the long run, it shows that an increase in the contribution of value added tax to tax revenue will produce a 28.87% reduction in tax revenue, although at a 10% level of significance.

Table 4: ARDL Estimates

Dependent Variable: LTAXR

Long run estimates				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CVAT	-0.288708	0.152321	-1.8954	0.0651
CFTAX	0.019881	0.20591	0.096552	0.9236
CCIED	0.000929	0.218334	0.004257	0.9966
Short run estimates				
D(CVAT)	0.02432	0.01975	1.23145	0.2306
D(CVAT(-1))	-0.13922	0.02161	-6.44305	0
D(CVAT(-2))	-0.04594	0.01265	-3.63322	0.0014
D(CCIED)	-0.03162	0.01662	-1.90233	0.0697
D(CCIED(-1))	0.01051	0.00466	2.25655	0.0338
CointEq(-1)*	-0.33179	0.04613	-7.19227	0
R-squared	0.976565		F-statistic(Prob)	89.29551 (0.000)
Adjusted R-squared	0.965629		Durbin-Watson stat	2.038782

Source: Authors’ computation

An increase in the contribution of custom, import and excise duties and Firs tax both have a positive impact on tax revenue in the current quarter by 0.0929% and 1.9881%, respectively and they are all not significant at 1% or 5%. In the short run, the result indicates that an increase in the contribution of Value Added Tax to tax revenue will produce a 2.43% increase in tax revenue, although not significant. The coefficients of the contribution of custom, import and excise duties in the current lag have a negative and insignificant influence on tax revenue, while in the first leg, it has a positive and significant influence on tax revenue at 5% level of significance.

The coefficient of the contribution of value-

added tax in the current lag has a positive and insignificant influence on tax revenue, while in the first and second lag, it has a negative influence on tax revenue which is significant at 1%. It is observed that the ECM is negative, less than one and significant at 1%. This indicates that 33.18% of the past error is corrected in the current period in the system.

The study tested for normality test, heteroskedasticity, serial correlation, CUSUM and CUSUMSQ which is shown in Table 5. It showed that the variables are normally distributed, it is homoscedastic, and there is no serial correlation while the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ are stable. The CUSUM and CUSUMSQ graph is shown in Figure 1.

Table 5: Post Estimation tests for ARDL model

Post Estimation tests	
Normality: 0.946 (0.623)	Serial Correlation: 0.387 (0.684)
Heteroskedasticity: 1.136 (0.381)	CUSUMSQ: Within 5% lines
CUSUM: it is within 5% lines	

Source: Authors' computation

Figure 1: CUSUM and CUSUM squared graphs of ARDL model

Source: Author's compilation

In summary, VAT contributes negatively to tax revenue in both the short and long run. Among the other variables, Customs, Import and Excise duties (CCIED), and Firs Tax (FTAX) contribute positively to tax revenue in the short and long run. Ubesie (2019), Ofishe (2015), Odunsi (2022), Aworemi and Ajala (2013) result contradicts the findings of the study, but only Okoro and Onatuyeh (2018) findings are in line with the result obtained.

Conclusion

In this study, the contributory effect of value-added tax on the level of tax revenue in Nigeria has been examined to provide further evidence to the existing documented studies. The variables of the study are both integrated at the level and the first difference I (0) and I (1), respectively and the bound test is also co-integrated. The study used ARDL technique for estimation and the results show that value-added tax has both long-run and short-run effects on tax revenue with data from CBN statistical bulletin. The result indicates that VAT contributes negatively to tax revenue in both the short and long run. Among the other variables, Custom, Import and Excise Duties (CCIED) and Firs Tax (FTAX) contribute positively to tax revenue in the short and long run. It is recommended that government should work at the increasing the level of VAT in the country until it contributes positively to the overall tax revenue as well as the economy.

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